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Engineering Education Interdisciplinarity in Global Teams

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ABSTRACT

Multiple disciplines approach, which includes global enhanced interdisciplinarity, has been discussed in the engineering education context from the early 21st Century. There is very little disagreement about its importance for the engineers, the key question has been how to implement theory into practice both in the curriculum and in the actual learning enhancement phase. In this paper, we discuss how to mitigate the social distance in these global education teams and therefore how it becomes the primary management challenge for the global interdisciplinary team leader.

Flexibility and appreciation for diversity are at the heart of managing a global interdisciplinary team. Leaders must expect problems and patterns to change or repeat themselves as teams shift, disband, and regroup. Several strategies to enhance interdisciplinary teams in engineering education are presented.

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INTRODUCTION

Multiple disciplines approach, which includes global enhanced interdisciplinarity, has been discussed in the engineering education context from the early 21st Century. There is very little disagreement about its importance for the engineers, the key

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question has been how to implement theory into practice both in the curriculum and in the actual learning enhancement phase.

If we try to answer the question what is driving global collaboration in higher education, then among the answers will for sure appear the following options:

- Funding
- Internationalization
- Cultural changes
- Cross-fertilization of ideas
- Intrinsic rewards

At the same time there are some global factors that have their impact at different scale in different areas including industry and engineering education as well. To succeed in the global economy today, more and more engineering companies are relying on a geographically dispersed workforce. They build teams that offer the best functional expertise from around the world, combined with deep, local knowledge of the most promising markets [1].

1 SOCIAL DISTANCE AND INTERDISCIPLINARY TEAM MANAGEMENT

It is important to understand what is the difference between global and local interdisciplinary teams. Creating successful work groups is hard enough when everyone is local and people share the same office space. But when team members come from different countries and functional backgrounds and are working in different locations, communication can rapidly deteriorate, misunderstanding can ensue, and cooperation can degenerate into distrust.

Teams that come from different fields or backgrounds, where people can interact formally and informally, align, and build trust refer to the local scale. For global teams it is common that coworkers do not only come from different fields, but are geographically separated, can't easily connect and align, so they experience high levels of social distance and struggle to develop effective interactions [2].

One basic difference between global interdisciplinary teams that work and those that don't lies in the level of social distance—the degree of emotional connection among team members.

In this paper, we discuss how to mitigate the social distance in these global education teams and therefore how it becomes the primary management challenge for the global interdisciplinary team leader. The management of the social distance is then paramount to identify and successfully improve the social distance. Leaders must expect problems and patterns to change or repeat themselves as teams shift, disband, and regroup. Several strategies to enhance interdisciplinary teams in engineering education are presented (Fig.1).

Fig. 1. Management of the social distance

1.1 Structure and the Perception of Power

In the context of global interdisciplinary teams in engineering education, the structural factors determining social distance are the location and number of sites where team members are based and the number of educators who work at each site.

The fundamental issue here is the perception of power. If most team members are located in United States (US), for instance, with two or three in Russia and in Portugal, there may be a sense that the US members have more power. This imbalance sets up a negative dynamic. People in the larger (majority) group may feel resentment toward the minority group, believing that the latter will try to get away with contributing less than its fair share. Meanwhile, those in the minority group may believe that the majority is usurping what little power and voice they have.

To correct perceived power imbalances between different groups, a leader of a global enhanced interdisciplinary team needs to get three key messages across: who we are; what we do; and that I'm there for you (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Key messages

It is important that the answer to the who we are question is, that the the team is a single entity, even though individual members may be very different from one another. The leader should encourage sensitivity to differences but look for ways to bridge them and build unity. To bring people back together a leader for a global interdisciplinary team should create opportunities for employees to talk about their cultures, and instituted a zero- tolerance policy for displays of cultural insensitivity.

About the question of what we do, it is important to remind team members that they share a common purpose and to direct their energy toward team unit or the academic goals. The leader should periodically highlight how everyone's work fits into the course's overall strategy and advances its knowledge. For instance, during a weekly coordination conference call, a global team leader might review the group's performance relative to the academic objectives. The leader might also discuss the level of collective focus and sharpness the team needs in order to keep innovating.

About the question on if I'm there for you, team members located far from the leader require frequent contact with him or her. A brief phone call or e-mail can make all the difference in conveying that their contributions matter. The team appreciated his attention and became more cohesive as a result.

1.2 Process and the Importance of Empathy

It almost goes without saying that empathy helps reduce social distance. If colleagues can talk informally around a nice tea – whether about work or about personal matters

– they are more likely to develop an empathy that helps them interact productively in more-formal contexts. Because geographically dispersed team members lack regular face time, they are less likely to have a sense of mutual understanding. To foster this, global team leaders need to make sure they build the following “deliberate moments” into the process for meeting virtually: feedback on routine interactions; unstructured time; and time to disagree.

Feedback on routine interactions: Face-to-face visits are one, but not the only, way to acquire learning about the impacts of set work routines. Remote team members can also use the phone, e-mail, or even videoconferencing to check in with one another and ask how the collaboration is going. The point is that leaders and members of global enhanced interdisciplinary teams must actively elicit this kind of “reflected knowledge,” or awareness of how others see them.

Unstructured time: Think back to your last face-to-face meeting. During the first few minutes before the official discussion began, what was the atmosphere like? Were people comparing notes on the weather, their kids, that new restaurant in a town? Unstructured communication like this is positive, even when people are spread all over the world, small talk is still a powerful way to promote trust. Especially during the first meetings, take the lead in initiating informal discussions about work and non-work matters that allow team members to get to know their distant counterparts.

Time to disagree: Leaders should encourage disagreement both about the team’s tasks and about the process by which the tasks get done. The challenge, of course, is to take the heat out of the debate. Framing meetings as brainstorming opportunities lowers the risk that people will feel pressed to choose between sides. Instead, they will see an invitation to evaluate agenda items and contribute their ideas. As the leader, model the act of questioning to get to the heart of things. Solicit each team member’s views on each topic you discuss, starting with those who have the least status or experience with the group so that they don’t feel intimidated by others’ comments. This may initially seem like a waste of time, but if you seek opinions up front, you may make better decisions and get buy-in from more people.

1.3 Language and the Fluency Gap

Good communication among coworkers drives effective knowledge sharing, decision making, coordination, and, ultimately, performance. But in global teams, varying levels of fluency with the chosen common language are inevitable – and likely to heighten social distance. The team members who can communicate best in the organization’s lingua franca (usually English) often exert the most influence, while those who are less fluent often become inhibited and withdraw [3]. Mitigating these effects typically involves insisting that all team members respect three rules for communicating in meetings: dial down dominance; dial up engagement; and balance participation to ensure inclusion.

Dial down dominance: Strong speakers must agree to slow down their speaking pace and use fewer idioms, slang terms, local technical terms, and esoteric cultural references when addressing the group. They should limit the number of comments they make within a set time frame, depending on the pace of the meeting and the subject matter. They should actively seek confirmation that they’ve been understood,

and they should practice active listening by rephrasing others' statements for clarification or emphasis.

Dial up engagement: Less fluent speakers should monitor the frequency of their responses in meetings to ensure that they are contributing. Don't let them use their own language and have a teammate translate, because that can alienate others. As with fluent speakers, team members who are less proficient in the language must always confirm that they have been understood. Similarly, when listening, they should be empowered to say they have not understood something. It can be tough for nonnative speakers to make this leap, yet doing so keeps them from being marginalized.

Balance participation to ensure inclusion: Getting commitments to good speaking behavior is the easy part; making the behavior happen will require active management. Global team leaders must keep track of who is and isn't contributing and deliberately solicit participation from less fluent speakers. Sometimes it may also be necessary to get dominant-language speakers to dial down to ensure that the proposals and perspectives of less fluent speakers are heard.

1.4 Identity and the Mismatch of Perceptions

Globally enhanced interdisciplinary teams work, most smoothly, when members "get" where their colleagues are coming from. However, deciphering someone's identity and finding ways to relate is far from simple. People define themselves in terms of a multitude of variables—age, gender, nationality, ethnicity, religion, occupation, political ties, and so forth.

Although behavior can be revealing, particular behaviors may signify different things depending on the individual's identity. When adapting to a new cultural environment, a savvy leader will avoid making assumptions about what behaviors mean. Take a step back, watch, and listen. For example, in America, someone who says, "Yes, I can do this" likely means she is willing and able to do what you asked. In India, however, the same statement may simply signal that she wants to try – not that she's confident of success. Before drawing conclusions, therefore, ask a lot of questions. In the example just described, you might probe to see if the team member anticipates any challenges or needs additional resources. Asking for this information may yield greater insight into how the person truly feels about accomplishing the task. Misunderstandings are a major source of social distance and distrust, and global team leaders have to raise everyone's awareness of them. This involves mutual learning and teaching [4].

1.5 Technology and the Connection Challenge

The modes of communication used by global interdisciplinary teams must be carefully considered, because the technologies can both reduce and increase social distance. Videoconferencing, for instance, allows rich communication in which both context and emotion can be perceived. E-mail offers greater ease and efficiency but lacks contextual cues

Choosing between instant and delayed forms of communication can be especially challenging for global interdisciplinary teams. Instant technologies are valuable when leaders need to persuade others to adopt their viewpoint. But if they simply want to share information, then delayed methods such as e-mail are simpler, more efficient, and less disruptive to people's lives. Leaders must also consider the team's interpersonal dynamics. If the team has a history of conflict, technology choices that limit the opportunities for real-time emotional exchanges may yield the best results.

Decisions about structure create opportunities for good process, which can mitigate difficulties caused by language differences and identity issues. If leaders act on these fronts, while marshaling technology to improve communication among geographically dispersed colleagues, social distance is sure to shrink, not expand.

2 INTERDISCIPLINARY ENVIRONMENT AT UNIVERSITIES

A successful interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary teaching/learning depends on the general team dynamics. Flexibility and appreciation for diversity are at the heart of managing a global interdisciplinary team. But university managers who actually lead engineering faculties are usually not so focused in building global teams for engineering education [5]. What are the reasons why interdisciplinary global teams in engineering are not so widespread as they could be?

The lack of interest in global interdisciplinary work in academic world could be explained by:

- Tradition
- Academic reward system
- Insufficient funding
- Time
- Attitudes
- Performance evaluation system
- Learning styles
- Communication across disciplines

This topic was of utmost interest at the Network International Conference “Interdisciplinarity in Engineering Education: Global Trends and Management Concepts – SYNERGY” that took place in Russia, 2016 [6]. Within the conference more than 40 participants, took part in the expert workshop «Managing university environment for interdisciplinary projects implementation: conditions, grants, consortium partnership». Participants acting in the role of experts evaluated the current state of interdisciplinary environment at Russian and foreign universities based on their personal experience and expert opinion [7]. Experts had to choose from the list of rates:

- critically low;
- low;
- average;
- high;
- excellent;
- other opinion.

According to the obtained results most participants from Russia estimate the level of interdisciplinary environment as critically low or low – 30%, average – 44% and high - 26%. Among representatives of HEIs from USA, Hungary, Czech Republic, Spain, Portugal, Republic of Kazakhstan, Peoples Republic of China the evaluation results were more positive: critically low – 13%, average - 25, and high – 63%, as shown at Fig. 3.

Fig.3. Expert evaluation of interdisciplinary environment at HEIs

While working in teams participants listed the following criteria to define the development of interdisciplinary environment at engineering HEI. Specific attributes for assessing the state of interdisciplinary environment at universities were proposed:

- Ratio of resources and infrastructure to develop interdisciplinary projects
- Involvement of stakeholders (transfer of knowledge)
- Curriculum (syllabus)
- Ratio of students involved in interdisciplinary projects (Teaching through projects)
- Ratio of staff, who completed professional development programs (each 3-5 years)
- Learning outcomes (knowledge & ability)
- Legal requirements
- Management structure.

Teamwork was followed by an open discussion that identified the key obstacles on the way for resolving the problem. Among the major barriers to develop interdisciplinary environment at university the experts named the following, being quite unanimous in their views:

1. Lack of innovative environment (infrastructure)
2. Learning outcomes do not include interdisciplinary aspect
3. Lack of motivation among the teaching staff and students, psychological unpreparedness
4. Lack of political (top management) support
5. Resistance to change the environment, organizational barriers
6. Resistance to share knowledge and ideas
7. Faculty is overloaded with routine tasks
8. Inflexibility or absence of a regulatory framework for interdisciplinary global interaction
9. Lack of assessment system for interdisciplinary projects, lack of experts to review

10. Lack of understanding the role of leader to generate ideas and run interdisciplinary projects
11. Low level of motivation for cooperation between universities and industry
12. Teachers do not want to leave their comfort zone to get involved in interdisciplinary cooperation.

3 FINAL WORDS

There is no doubt anymore that global collaboration is one of the most important skills of the graduates of the 21st century. Universities need to break down “silos”, resolve “turf” issues and embark in inter/multi-disciplinary global collaboration. Individual silos, “self-interest”, is human nature... but imagine the impact if we think in terms of long-term prosperity instead of short-term greed. Silos everywhere hinder our ability to address the interdisciplinary problems we face. Professors need to learn to work in global teams and be role models for the future generations. In this model, everyone is a teacher and a learner, which enables people to step out of their traditional roles. Team members take on more responsibility for the development of the team as a whole. Leaders learn to see themselves as unfinished and are thus more likely to adjust their style to reflect the team’s needs. Embrace and learn from mistakes... nobody is perfect!

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